

CAST 5th NEWSLETTER

November 2022

Active Monitoring of Cancer AS an Alternative To Surgery

MARIE SKLODOWSKA-CURIE GRANT PROJECT

Colophon

The CAST Newsletter is to inform all participants and those interested in the CAST. We will share publications, presentations and news. The CAST Newsletter is also sent to participants in the IWWD-consortium.

If you like to be added to the mailing list or if you want to be removed, please mail to CAST@lumc.nl

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Early Stage Researchers

This Newsletter was created by the 15 CAST ESRs together:

Bharti, Ilaria, Somayeh, Shabnam, Sofieke, Rita, Lishan, Ignacio, Bitu, Ngu, Felicia, Francesco, Ana and Elham.

Courses and ESR meetings

On June 23rd to 24th 2022, all the ESRs of the CAST consortium attended the ESSO Course on Fluorescence-Guided Surgery in Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC). The next week from June 28th to 29th 2022 ESRs attended the "Career Sailing Event" at Heinrich-Heine-Universität Dusseldorf, along with ESRs from PAVE, NOVA-MRI and RISE-WELL. We would also like to share an excerpt from our monthly ESR meetings conducted online.

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ESRs in Conferences

The laparoscopic colorectal course was organized at IRCAD. Here in the picture, Michele Diana speaks about the CAST project, in particular about targeted fluorescence. In the second picture Rita Rodriguez presenting her work "Nieuwe ontwikkelingen naast en in combinatie met fluorescentie-geleide chirurgie" as an invited lecture at the first Dutch Fluorescence-Guided Surgery Symposium.

Bharti Arora gave a talk on imaging biomarkers in Colorectal Cancer at the International Conference in Systems Biology 2022, organized in Berlin in October.

She also presented her work at the Young Cancer Scientist Symposium 2022 organized at the University Medical Centre Göttingen (UMG) in November.

Somayah attended NWO CHAINS 2022, the annual Dutch chemistry conference on 21 & 22 September. She met a lot of people from different part of Netherlands and Europe. In addition, she learnt a lot of information in her field. Here is something that caught her interest: The role of chemistry in painting and art. How could be possible to discover the secrets of painters by chemistry after many years.

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ESRs in Conferences

Elham Zonoobi and Ana Matoshi presented their research poster for the characterization of tumor markers on colorectal carcinoma extracellular vesicles at NLSEV 2022- Netherlands Society for Extracellular Vesicles, organized in Maastricht in November.

Shabnam Thapa presented her research posters in two conferences. She presented her poster about cost-effectiveness of surgery versus watch-and-wait strategy in rectal cancer at the Greater Manchester Cancer Conference held at Manchester, UK on 18th – 19th October.

She presented her poster about value frameworks assessing interventions for cancer treatment at the ISPOR Europe held at Vienna, Austria on 6th-9th November.

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ESRs attending specialised courses

From September 1st to 7th Ilaria followed the course “The path to better care for colorectal cancer patients” organized by the OOA (Oncologie Onderzoekshooschool Amsterdam).

During 5 days, the course gave a very broad overview of the various directions of research in the immense field of colorectal cancer, trying to pull together the important achievements of fundamental research and the activity of clinical researchers and define a unique road from the bench to the bedside.

Oncologie Onderzoekshooschool Amsterdam
Oncology Graduate School

COURSE

The path to better care for colorectal cancer patients

A significant part of the course was dedicated to the presentation of milestone studies about many aspects of the development and the treatment of CRC. This way we as participants were motivated to get deeper in the understanding of fields of research we were least familiar with.

As a clinician she particularly appreciated learning about the great amount of high-quality science that is trying to explain the etiology, to ease the diagnosis and to personalize the treatment of colorectal cancer patients. Also, towards the end of the course, she loved hearing how some of these discoveries were translated into clinical studies towards a better and more personalized care of the very heterogeneous group of colorectal cancer patients. She is excited to follow similar courses and stay up to date on the very exciting discoveries in the field of rectal cancer research.

Farewell corner:

On Monday 14th November 2022 Ilaria and Sofieke were present when prof. dr. Cornelis J.H. van de Velde spoke his farewell lecture at the University of Leiden. Cornelis van de Velde obtained his doctorate cum laude in 1977 and became a surgeon in 1982. Five years later, he was appointed professor of Surgical Oncology. In the 1990s, he founded multidisciplinary groups that contributed to better treatments in the Netherlands in the field of breast, colorectal and gastric cancer. He initiated several practice changing studies that not only improved the survival of patients, but also their quality of life.

Cornelis van de Velde was the lead investigator in ground breaking trials leading to better local control and survival for rectal cancer patients and was part of the formation of the International Watch & Wait Database (IWWD). One of Cornelis van de Velde's qualities was to form international multidisciplinary networks to collaborate in trials and research. CAST is a good example of such a network, where he has played an important role in its founding and connecting the multiple international partners and organizations.

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A glance at a life of an ESR

Learning sweet skills along with Ph.D.

I recently took part in a bake-off and cake sale for the fundraising event 'Rewrite Cancer' organised at my workplace; Manchester Cancer Research Centre. For this occasion, I baked 'Strawberry Swirled Greek Yoghurt Cake'. Even though the name of the cake is a bit mouthful, the process of making it was quite satisfying. But I would not have dared to even lift a spoon to bake a year ago. Growing up in Nepal, I always saw baking as something complicated as it came with specific instructions for measuring ingredients. Whereas in my country, we rather tend to go with our intuition (and heart) rather than measuring spoons and cups. Besides, houses in Nepal usually don't have an oven and baking is something that is left to a bakery. If I had to eat a pastry or a cake, I would simply go to one of the bakeries. So, I always had reservations to try baking.

However, my reservations about baking changed to curiosity when I moved to Manchester last year to do my Ph.D. During my initial months in Manchester, I shared a house with a fantastic home baker. She used to bake sourdough bread, cakes and cookies over the weekends. She used to watch her and try to learn how to bake. Seeing her converting flour, some eggs and butter into delicious treats made me want to try my hands at baking.

Finally, one day I decided to try baking. After watching multiple videos, and reading multiple recipes, I felt confident enough to bake Banana Bread. I know it's pretty basic and seems like everyone made it during lockdown but for me it seemed like a puzzle. Being a person who always measures ingredients by eyes and intuition, for the first time in my life, I followed step-by-step instruction. I waited patiently in front of the oven and was delighted when the bread started to rise. With that first bake, I celebrated Nepali New Year (we celebrate our New Year in March). After making banana bread successfully, I ventured out to sponge cakes, oatmeal cookies and recently muffins.

As I started to bake more, I could see it is not that different from doing research work. When I start a research project, I set a goal, similarly in baking I decide the type of cake that I want to make. Then, I go through multiple recipes to gather information on how to make the cake. Likewise, I do literature review and go through numerous papers to gather information on topic of the research. Then comes setting objectives and planning how I will achieve my research goal. In baking, I collect the ingredients that I need and prepare a recipe to make the cake. The method that I apply in research is like the measurement of ingredients for the cake. Then applying those research methods, I conduct my research and analyse the results which in a way is like putting the cake batter in the oven and waiting for it to convert into cake.

My bakes are sometimes hit and sometimes miss, which happens in research as well. Whatever the result is, I find baking relaxing and it teaches me to not to give up and try the recipe one more time with more precision. I use same attitude in my PhD work and retry again when I don't achieve my goals. And if life gets too stressful, I just need a bite of home baked cake to relax and start again.

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